

EFFECT OF AEROBIC TRAINING ON VERTICAL JUMPING ABILITY OF MALE BOXERS OF MUMBAI

Prof. Jaysing M. Hotkar

BPCA's College of Physical Education, Wadala, Mumbai-31.

Paper Received On: 21 October 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 25 November 2025

Published On: 01 December 2025

INTRODUCTION

Physical exercise is essential for maintaining health, improving fitness, and enhancing overall quality of life. Among the various forms of physical activity, aerobic and anaerobic exercises are two fundamental categories that differ in intensity, energy systems, and physiological benefits. Understanding these differences is important for athletes, students, trainers, and anyone seeking balanced fitness development.

Aerobic exercise, often referred to as “cardio,” involves continuous and rhythmic physical activity performed at a moderate intensity over an extended period. The term ‘aerobic’ means with oxygen, highlighting that this type of exercise relies on oxygen to generate energy. During aerobic exercise, the heart and lungs work efficiently to supply oxygen to the working muscles. Activities such as jogging, cycling, swimming, and brisk walking are common forms of aerobic exercise. The selected dependent variable focuses on anaerobic ability, which involves short, explosive bursts of activity primarily powered by stored muscle energy via the ATP–PC system. This differs from aerobic exercise, which relies on sustained, lower-intensity activity supported by oxygen uptake. The ATP–PC (phosphate) and glycaemic (anaerobic glycolysis) systems are the two primary anaerobic energy systems responsible for ATP resynthesis during high-intensity efforts. While these systems differ from the aerobic energy system in terms of fuel source, duration, and intensity, both aerobic and anaerobic pathways contribute significantly to overall physical fitness. Vertical jumping ability is particularly important for boxers, as it reflects lower-body power and the effective transfer of force from the legs through the core, ultimately enhancing punching power. The objective of the study was to examine the effect of aerobic training on the vertical jump performance of male boxers.

In a review study conducted (Keating, Coveney, McAuliffe, & Higgins, 2022 August) in the conclusion it was mentioned that 14 studies were included in the systematic review. Interventions ranged from cycling, aerobic exercises, walking, yoga, or combined aerobic and resistance exercises. Of the studies identified, none directly compared aerobic exercise with strength training. Half of the studies showed benefit in glycaemic control with additional exercise compared with usual physical activity.

(Alawna, Amro, & Mohamed, 2020) The review was conducted to systematically analyse the effects of aerobic exercise on immunological biomarkers to provide safe aerobic exercise recommendations and specifications for patients with COVID-19. This review demonstrated that patients with COVID-19 should follow a regular program of aerobic exercise for 20-60 min. This program should be in the form of cycling or walking with an intensity of 55%-80% VO₂max or 60%-80% of maximum heart rate.

(Wilson, et al.) The primary objective of this investigation was to identify which components of endurance training are detrimental to resistance training outcomes. The results of the study shows no significant relationship between endurance training and resistance training outcomes.

The above-presented studies, particularly those related to blood glycaemic levels, muscular strength, and heart rate, demonstrate significant improvements. These findings indicate that various types of aerobic exercises, when systematically manipulated, are effective in enhancing overall health as well as physical and motor fitness components. On this basis, the present study entitled “Effect of Aerobic Training on Vertical Jump Performance of Male Boxers in Mumbai” was conducted. The methodology, including sampling procedures, findings, and conclusions of the study, are presented below.

METHODOLOGY

- **Research Design**

For the present study, The Post-test Only Control Group Design of the True Experimental Research Design was used to control the pre testing threats.

- **Sampling**

A multistage sampling method was employed to select the participants for the study. In the first stage, the researcher obtained a list of academies conducting boys’ boxing activities. From this list, one academy namely ‘Education and Welfare Foundation’s Boxing Academy, Nagpada, Mumbai, was randomly selected. Subsequently, based on the academy records, boys’ boxing players aged 14 to 16 years were identified, from which forty (n = 40) school-level

boxers were randomly selected for the experiment. The selected participants were then randomly assigned into Control Group (n=20) and Experimental Group (n = 20). Experimental Group was received manipulated Aerobic Training for daily one hour in the evening from 7:00 pm to 8:00 pm. Except Sundays and public holidays, whereas Control Group did not receive Aerobic training. Both groups were allowed to participate in their daily routine activities.

- **Collection of Data**

As per the research design, the vertical jump performance data of both the control and experimental groups were collected after the aerobic training intervention using the Vertical Jump Test. The centimetre unite of length measurement was used for data collection.

RESULT ON VERTICAL JUMP TEST

Table 1

Mean Scores, Standard Deviation and 'N' of Control Group, and Experimental Group of Vertical Jump Test.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Control Group	20	30.95	5.07
Experimental Group	20	34.85	5.47

In Table-1, it can be seen that the mean scores of Vertical Jump Test of Control Group is 30.95 whereas the standard deviation score is 5.07centimeteres. In case of Experimental Group the mean score is 34.85 centimetres and the standard deviation of the same is 5.47. in the above table it can be realised that, the experimental group is differ by 3.9 centimetre. It is essential to know that whether the obtained mean difference score is significantlly differ from each other or not one way ANOVA test was performed with the help of IBM Statistical Package of Social Sciences and the obtained results are presented in table-2. The sample size (n = 20) remains consistent across both the groups to ensuring equal representation and minimizing any discrepancies that could arise from unequal sample sizes.

Table 2

Comparison of the mean scores of Vertical Jump of Control Group and Experimental Group

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remarks
Between Groups	152.10	1	152.10	5.47	0.025	$p < 0.05^*$
Within Groups	1057.50	38	27.83			
Total	1209.60	39				

It can be seen that in the above Table 2, in case of Comparison of the mean scores of Vertical Jump Test of Control Group and Experimental Group the value of Sum of Squares and Mean Square is 152.10 with the 'df' value 1. The value of 'F' ratio is 5.47 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance ($P < 0.05^*$), thus the stated null hypothesis that 'there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Control Group, Experimental Group with respect to Vertical Jump' is rejected. Therefore, it is interpreted that the selected Aerobic Training is effective in improving of Vertical Jump Ability of the boxing players aged 14 to 16 years.

Figure 1

Mean Scores of Vertical Jump of Control Group and Experimental Group.

CONCLUSION

Overall, based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that the mean score of Vertical Jump of Experimental Group is significantly improved. Therefore, it can be says that the manipulated 'Aerobic Training' is helpful to improve the Vertical Jumping ability of the male students of Mumbai.

REFERENCES

- Alawna, M., Amro, M., & Mohamed, A. A. (2020, December). Aerobic exercises recommendations and specifications for patients with COVID-19: a systematic review. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci*, 24(24);, *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci*. doi:10.26355/eurrev_202012_24211
- Almeida, M. B., Gil, C., & Araújo, S. (2003). Effects of aerobic training on heart rate. *Rev Bras Med Esporte*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1517-86922003000200006>
- Keating, N., Coveney, C., McAuliffe, F. M., & Higgins, M. F. (2022 August). Aerobic or Resistance Exercise for Improved Glycaemic Control and Pregnancy Outcomes in Women with Gestational Diabetes Mellitus: A Systematic Review. doi:10.3390/ijerph191710791
- Wilson, J. M., Marin, P. J., Rhea, M. R., Wilson, S. M., Loenneke, J. P., & Anderson, J. C. (n.d.). Concurrent training: a meta-analysis examining interference of aerobic and resistance exercises. doi:10.1519/JSC.0b013e31823a3e2d